

Guidelines Document: Metadata Template Version Control

Written by: Ami Saji, Laura Morales, Dimitrios-Rafail Tservenis

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OPENMIN

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COST Action 16111 - ETHMIGSURVEYDATA

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Introduction

To ensure that the data producers/metadata contributors (hereafter the contributors) have correctly coded metadata for a survey, each record needs to be reviewed by the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA central team (hereafter the administrators), led by Laura Morales. **This guidelines document, therefore, outlines how each survey record should be reviewed and handled to ensure proper version control.** The document is structured into the following sections:

1. Overview of the Quality Control Process: A detailed explanation of how the overall quality control process is structured
2. Quality Control workflow: A step-by-step guide on how to conduct the quality control of a survey record.

For anyone contributing to and assisting with the version control of the records, they must first read this guidelines document to ensure that they are executing and completing the steps correctly. Any questions about the version control of the records can be directed to the administrators (ethmigsurveydata@sciencespo.fr).

1. Overview of the Quality Control Process Governing Metadata Submission Through the Registry Back End

The quality control process for the survey records contributed through the Registry's back end consists of the following steps:

1. The contributors (i.e., data producers/metadata contributors) submit the survey record for initial quality control.
2. The administrators (i.e., the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA central team) complete a "first-stage" quality control by reviewing the submitted survey record and providing (via email) detailed feedback to the contributors.
3. The contributors update their records using the feedback provided. If their record had serious mistakes (which is communicated to them by the reviewer), they need to submit their record for a "second round" of quality control.
4. The contributors submit the final version of their record for a final quality check.
5. The ETHMIGSURVEYDATA central team conducts the final quality control of the record by reviewing and making any straightforward edits/modifications to it.

**** IMPORTANT NOTE**:** Explicit consent to store and reuse the survey metadata is needed if the survey has been deposited to a data archive/repository where metadata describing the survey has already been produced. In such a case, the data archive/repository will be asked to provide this consent. For surveys that are

not publicly available through a data archive/repository platform, implicit consent to store and use the survey metadata is needed from the survey owner/producer (e.g., independent researcher/research team). The consent will be requested by the administrators.

Figure 1: Quality Control Workflow

2. Detailed Quality Control Steps

The first-stage quality control begins when contributors submit a record to the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA administrators for initial review. Whenever contributors finish filling out the online form via the back end of the Registry and are ready to have the metadata for their

survey reviewed by the administrators, they need to notify the latter by emailing the sshoc.project@sciencespo.fr account. Upon receiving this notification email, an administrator should confirm receipt of this email and then proceed with the quality control process.

To provide correct and appropriate feedback, **the reviewer should first (re)read the [EMM Survey Registry Back-end User Guide](#)** to ensure they are fully familiar with how contributors have been asked to code survey metadata. **After reading this document, the reviewer should** proceed with the quality control process as described below:

1. Log in to the [back-end of the Registry](#) using their issued account.
2. Click on 'Surveys' on the left-hand side of the welcome page to access all the metadata available via the back end.
3. Locate, in the list of surveys, the record (i.e., the filled-out online form) that contains all the metadata provided by the contributor for their survey. The easiest way to locate the record-of-interest is by searching via the unique ID (a four-digit number auto-generated and assigned whenever a contributor first saves what they have input into the online form by clicking on the 'Save Survey' button).
4. Open up the record by clicking on the pen and paper icon on the right-hand side.

NOTE: If there is no pen and paper icon next to the record (or for any of the records), this means the account has not been set up with administrative rights. In such cases, ask Laura Morales to re-configure the account as 'Administrator.'

TIP: For surveys captured as multiple records (e.g., cross-country surveys), it is generally easier to review these records jointly. To do this, select (by clicking on the empty box on the left-hand side) all the relevant records, click on 'Select Action' in the upper right-hand corner, select 'Export CSV' from the drop-down menu that is presented, click on the blue play button icon next to 'Select Action, and then click on 'Run Action' from the displayed pop up menu. This should then export a CSV file, containing all the metadata for the selected records, which can be opened up using Microsoft Excel.

5. Document all feedback (e.g., discrepancies in the metadata, required fields left empty, responses that are written in an unclear manner) that needs to be provided to the contributor using a Word document. Carefully review and correct, as needed, the metadata produced by the contributor for their survey record following the steps outlined in the next section (see ***QC guidelines for reviewing and cleaning the metadata***).
6. Email the finalized feedback to the contributor and CC the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA central team email (ethmigsurveydata@sciencespo.fr). In the body of the email, explain and emphasize that the record cannot be published until all feedback points are addressed. Also, invite the contributor to react to each feedback point by commenting directly on the Word document.

NOTE: It is highly unlikely that a record will have no feedback. It generally requires a few rounds of back and forth between the contributor and the reviewer for all feedback points to be resolved.

7. Once all the feedback points have been resolved with the contributor, email the contributors to inform them that the record has been updated and is ready to be published. In your email, invite them to review the record to ensure they are happy with the final metadata.

8. Once the contributor confirms they are satisfied with the final metadata, log in to the back end and open the record one last time.
 - A. At the top, change the record's status to 'Publish.'
 - B. Assign and add the ID number (field 1.1) for the record by consulting the file, [Ques 1.1 Unique ID Tracker.xlsx](#). If the survey is also part of a larger study, please assign and add the unique identifier for the larger study (field 2.1) for the record by consulting the file [Unique ID \(2.1\) Tracker: Larger Studies](#), as well. As a note, both files detail how to assign and keep track of the unique identifiers.
 - C. Fill out section 11. In particular, in 11.1, you will need to add information about who compiled the metadata and in 11.2, the date when this file was last updated. To fill out 11.3-11.7 fields, you will need to extract the respective information from another record of the same country for which you compiled metadata through the Registry.
 - D. Click 'Save/Update Survey' to instantaneously publish and display the record on the front end.
9. Notify the contributor through email that their record has been successfully published and is now visible on the front end.

A. Quality control guidelines for reviewing and cleaning the contributed metadata

For each record as a whole:

1. Check that the contributors: (i) provided responses for the most essential variables (i.e. those with a red asterisk placed next to the variable name), (ii) correctly coded the responses following the instructions provided in the [EMM Survey Registry Back-end User Guide](#) and (iii) provided responses that are generally logical and consistent (e.g., if they provide a response rate calculation, they should have also provided a response rate). For any variable with a missing or unclear response, provide a comment (i.e., why the variable needs to be filled out and/or how the contributor can correct it).
2. Check all the open response variables to ensure that the metadata contributors have used proper nouns that are consistent with the standardization rules outlined in [Appendix D](#). When the template includes a mistake of this sort, correct the field in question.
3. For any variable that has a response with a typing/data entry,¹ or a small/obvious spelling, grammatical, and/or punctuation error,² correct the mistake directly whenever you feel confident about this correction.
4. Try to code a response for each of those variables with a drop-down menu or default accepted values. For any variable where a response cannot be provided by you and/or input from the contributors is needed, add a comment in your feedback.

¹ This refers to any typing or data entry errors that can be easily corrected by the reviewer. Examples include changing a N/A response to -999. Not applicable (e.g. variable 1.2) or removing the % symbol, from a response rate (e.g. variable 5.3).

² For spelling, grammar and punctuation, UK or US writing conventions can be used.

5. Dates need to follow the format 'yyyy/mm/dd' and figures relating to sample sizes should not include any comma or dot to separate the thousands (e.g., change 1,235 to 1235, and 1.235 to 1235). Please correct all fields that do not respect the aforementioned date and number formats.
6. Double-check the open response variables (particularly the comments section for each section) to ensure that the information provided can be displayed on the Registry (e.g., if in 10.2 the data quality is described as being "very bad because of the poor survey design", the comment should be adapted to be more diplomatic). Please edit and modify the language whenever necessary and explain to the contributor why the content of the field was modified. In addition, please ask them to review and validate the edits made.

B. Quality control guidelines by section/variable

1. **1.7a:** If it is a subnational survey record, code var. 1.7a using a single region name in English that will be used for sorting on the online database. Which region to choose? Choose in the first instance the region that seems more important in the study in terms of sample size (in variable 5.2 or 5.9). If all regions had the same sample size or no information about sub-sample sizes is available, then choose the one with a larger target population (in variable 3.5), and if this information is not available, the first one in alphabetical order in English (variable 1.7).
2. **1.8b.** If it is a subnational survey record, conversion from a LAU/NUTS code to a subnational area for most of the countries included in the Registry can be found here, [EU 28 - Subnational Area Types \(LAU and NUTS\).xlsx](#), OR here, [Methodological manual on territorial typologies](#). For the former document, please locate the sheet for the country you are reviewing (the sheets are labelled by country name in ISO code) and consult the DEGURBA column (1 = cities, 2 = suburbs/towns, 3 = rural); in the case this column is blank or has been filled out as "n.a", notify the administrators via email, mark the affected cells in red, and on the feedback document explain that the administrators/central team are looking into the correct conversion as this information has not been made readily available by EUROSTAT.
3. **Section 2.** Double-check the responses in section 2 to make sure they have been correctly filled out. For example, if a survey is identified as being a single cross-section, then the sub-section in section 2 for longitudinal/repeated surveys (i.e., section 2b) should not be filled out. Another example is that if a survey is part of an international survey program, then not only section 2c should be filled out, but 2.5 should be filled out, too. Please remember that if any field requires input/action from the contributors, a corresponding comment should be added to the feedback.
4. **2.6 & 2.9.** Ensure that surveys belonging to an international survey program have coded 2.6 and 2.9 to reflect the starting date of the survey series in the given country reflected by the record. In other words, 2.6 and 2.9 should not list the starting date for the international survey program as a whole UNLESS the surveys for the given country had the same starting date.

5. **Section 2.** In case of **longitudinal surveys** with multiple cohorts, make sure that section 2 is coded so that all waves, regardless of the cohort being surveyed, are treated as “belonging” to the same “larger study”. For example, if survey X had 2 cohorts, one that started in 1998 (respondents surveyed in 2000 and 2002) and another that started in 2004 (respondents surveyed in 2006 and 2007), then: (i) 2.6 would be coded so that all waves of the 1998 and 2004 cohorts have the same start date (i.e. the start date of the 1998 cohort); (ii) 2.7 would be coded to reflect how frequently the survey has occurred taking into account both the 1998 and 2004 cohorts (i.e. irregular, every 1-2 years); (iii) 2.8 would be coded so that the first iteration of the 1998 cohort is wave 1, the second iteration of the 1998 cohort is wave 2, the first iteration of the 2004 cohort is wave 3, etc.; and (iv) 2.15 would be coded to include a comment about the wave order for each cohort (e.g. for wave 3, you would code, “wave 3 of survey X is the first time the 2004 cohort was surveyed), given that we’re counting the waves collectively for the 2 cohorts in 2.8.
6. **Section 2.** In case of surveys that are a part of an **international survey** programme and administered in at least 2 of the countries included in the Registry, consult the Excel file, [List of International Surveys](#), for filling in 2.9 and 2.10. Then update the sheet accordingly, following the instructions you find in it. Check the Excel file, [Unique ID Tracker: Larger Studies](#), to see if any other country has already coded this survey on the Registry. If yes, use the information coded onto the other country’s record to help you check and correct (if necessary) the entries for section 2. Also, if you identify any international surveys on the template that have not been included in the [List of International Surveys](#), please add them.
7. **3.1a.** EMM target population with terms standardized: This variable is being post-coded by breaking down the EMM target population description into larger/general key terms (Example: If the EMM target population was defined as “First generation immigrants of Pakistani or Moroccan origin”, it would be post-coded as: Pakistani; Moroccan; First generation migrants). Use the following Google Drive sheet, [EMM Target population standardized](#), to ensure that you post-code this variable correctly; more detailed instructions have also been provided on the “Instructions” tab of that file, and it is imperative that you read the contents on this tab BEFORE post-coding this variable.]
8. **3.4.** For all **general population surveys** (though ideally for all surveys), please double-check that variable 3.4 has at least one “Yes” response; this is because at least one EMM-related question is needed in order for a survey to count as an EMM survey. If 3.4 has not been coded with at least a “Yes” response, please make sure you provide a comment in the feedback.
9. **3.6.** In case of surveys that have included a **partitioned majority subgroup** (i.e. a “yes” response to variable 3.6), make sure that: (i) **section 5** captures the sample size information for ALL the survey respondents, (ii) **variable 5.9** includes a comment explaining that **section 5** provides the sample size information for the survey as a whole and that **section 6** is where the partitioned subgroup sample size information can be

found; and (iii) section 6 captures the sample size information for the majority subgroup (as well as any other subgroups that have resulted from partitioning). For surveys that are not general population surveys AND have had section 6 filled out by the contributors (because the survey partitioned the EMM respondents), make sure that section 5 captures the sample size information for ALL the survey respondents and section 6 captures the sample size information for ALL of the partitioned subgroups (if there are more than 5 subgroups, then all remaining subgroups should be documented in the comments section of section 6) In case of EU-LFS waves or Roma-targeted surveys by UNDP and/or FRA, do an extra careful check of these by consulting how such surveys/waves were previously documented on the Registry.

10. **3.6a.** Survey designed as a general population survey: Select the appropriate response from the list options.
11. **4.4.** Check variable 4.4 to ensure that a proper sampling frame has been listed. During this re-check, you should also re-review the information provided in variables **4.2-4.3** to see if the sampling frame coded in variable 4.4 seems appropriate. For example, if in variables **4.2-4.3** the sampling method is described as using random routes, then a census/population register type sampling frame would not be suitable; instead, the sampling frame listed should be a list of addresses or location-based starting points.
12. In case of **general population surveys**, if the survey **has been partitioned** to have an EMM subgroup (and/or any other subgroups), make sure that: (i) **section 5** captures the sample size information for ALL the survey respondents and not just the EMM respondents; (ii) variable 5.9 includes a comment explaining that section 5 provides the sample size information for the survey as a whole and that **section 6** is where the EMM-specific sample size information (as well as all other subgroups) can be found; and (iii) section 6 captures the sample size information for the EMM respondents (as well as any other subgroups that have resulted from partitioning). If, however, the survey **has NOT been partitioned** to have any subgroups, including EMM respondents, make sure that: (i) section 5 captures the sample size information for ALL the survey respondents; (ii) **variable 5.9** includes a comment explaining that section 5 provides the sample size information for the survey as a whole; and (iii) variable 5.9, instead of section 6, captures the (estimated) EMM sample size information. If you have any questions about how to handle general population surveys or need further assistance, please contact the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA central team.
13. **7.5a.** Migrant languages in ISO code [Note: ISO 639-3 should be used, available [here](#)]. ISO codes should be listed in all caps and separated with a semicolon.
14. **7.7a.** Questionnaire in migrant language in ISO code [Note: ISO 639-3 should be used, available [here](#)]. ISO codes should be listed in all caps and separated with a semicolon.
15. **8.9a.** Dataset languages in ISO code [Note: ISO 639-3 should be used, available [here](#)]. ISO codes should be listed in all caps and separated with a semicolon.

16. **8.15a.** Language(s) of technical survey documentation in ISO code [Note: ISO 639-3 should be used, available [here](#)]. ISO codes should be listed in all caps and separated with a semicolon.
17. **8.20a.** Language(s) of survey questionnaire in ISO code [Note: ISO 639-3 should be used, available [here](#)]. ISO codes should be listed in all caps and separated with a semicolon.
18. Make sure that variables **8.4, 8.13, and 8.19** have been coded in http format (e.g., <https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771073>). Please correct all DOIs that are not written in http format.

The completion of all steps above signifies that the record's quality control process has been completed successfully.

Appendix A: Sample Word Document (Template for providing Quality Control feedback)

Below is an example of how the reviewer could provide feedback to the contributor when completing the quality control.

General Comments

- You have generally done a good job, but there are some issues with completeness or misunderstandings that need to be corrected for the survey record you have compiled.
- The feedback is structured by variable: Detailed comments have been provided below for any field (i.e., variable or response) that requires your attention. Example:

National Survey

- 2.9 + 2.10: You indicate that this survey is part of an international survey; however, you do not list the other countries that participate in this larger study in var. 2.5, and that's contradictory.
- 4.1 + 4.2: I think you just missed these ones!
- 4.4: This field should be filled in. If no sampling frame is used, say "no sampling frame used."

Subnational survey

- 1.8a: You said n.a. (not available) for the NUTS/LAU code for Konik. You need, however, to put a code here. At the very least, this would be the LAU1 code for Podgorica (as I understand that Konik is within the municipality of Podgorica), but it might be that MOSTAT has given Konik a LAU2 code as they have created codes also for "settlements" (see here: <https://www.monstat.org/userfiles/file/klasifikacije/statistical%20regions%20.pdf>). So I would suggest that you contact MOSTAT and request the list of codes for LAU1 and LAU2.
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Appendix B: Sample Emails for Quality Control

Subject: Survey record (ID number) feedback

Dear (*Names of contributors*),

Thank you for submitting your record for review. Overall, your record was (*quality of the template*) and I appreciate all the work and effort you have put in.

To this email, I have attached a Word document that provides detailed feedback about your record.

Thank you again for your contributions and please do not hesitate to reach out to me (*Reviewer's email address*) and the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA team (sshoc.project@sciencespo.fr) if you have any questions and/or concerns.

Note: If you DO NOT want to have your name displayed in Section 11 of the Registry, please send us an email stating that you do not want your name displayed on the registry. If no such email is received by (date selected), we will assume you are providing us with consent.

Warm regards,
(*Reviewer's name*)

Appendix C: Protocol for Coding Variables with “Missing” Responses

The table below shows, for each variable, the response options that can be used when a field has a missing response.

Variable (red = "compulsory")	Response type (closed, open)	Subnational only	Response option(s) when missing
1. General identification information about the survey			
1.0. Country	Closed	No	N/A - must be filled out
1.1. ID number (leave blank)	Open	No	N/A - to be filled out by the central team
1.2. Acronym	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
1.3. Survey Name Eng.	Open	No	N/A - must be filled out
1.4. Survey Name Nat.	Open	No	N/A - must be filled out
1.5. Scope of survey	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.6. Which subnational level	Open	Yes	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.7. Name of region(s) Eng.	Open	Yes	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.8. Name of region(s) Nat.	Open	Yes	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.8a. If subnational, add the NUTS/LAU code of the specific cities/regions	Open	Yes	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.8b. If subnational, type of subnational area	Closed	Yes	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.9. Representative of the population	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.10. Type of survey	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.10a. If "other" in 1.10. specify	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999. Not applicable
1.11. Starting date of survey	Open	No	-99.Information not available
1.12. End date of survey	Open	No	-99.Information not available
1.12a. Survey in development/not yet completed	Closed	No	-9.Don't know

1.13. Main topic(s) in the survey			
1.13.1.Asylum seekers and refugee issues	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.2.Citizenship and naturalization	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.3.Economic, cultural, digital, leisure, and media consumption	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.4.Demographic characteristics/behaviours	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.5.Discrimination, racism, xenophobia, and/or social exclusion	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.6.Educational attainment/trajectory, human capital, skills	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.7.Family reunification, marriage, family relations	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.8.Gender relations, gender identity, sexuality	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.9.Housing/housing access	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.10.Health/health access	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.11.Human smuggling and trafficking	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.12.Identity (ethnic, national, racial, religious) and belonging	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.13.Financial situation and/or economic inequality	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.14.Interethnic contact & conflict	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.15.Labour market integration and/or socioeconomic mobility	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.16.Language skills/training	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.13.17.Leisure, sports, and art activities	Closed	No	-9.Don't know

1.13.18. Legal status/administrative situation	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.19. Migration trajectory (past/future)	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.20. Political inclusion and participation, and social/political attitudes	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.21. Public attitudes about migration and migrants	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.22. Reasons for migration/migration drivers	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.23. Return migration	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.24. Social cohesion and/or civic engagement and/or networks	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.25. Space use, spatial consequences	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.26. Time use	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.27. Transnational patterns (e.g. remittances, travel, engagement with 'home' country politics, etc.) and diasporas	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.28. Unaccompanied migrant minors	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.29. Religion	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.30. Welfare services access	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.31. Life quality/satisfaction and well-being	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.32. Policy/rights awareness	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.33. Other	Closed	No	-9. Don't know
1.13.33a. If "other" in 1.13, specify	Open	No	-9. Don't know -99. Information not available -999. Not applicable
1.14. Main purpose of the survey			
1.14.1. Research/academic	Closed	No	-9. Don't know

1.14.2.Public policy	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.14.3.Government statistics	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.14.4.NGO/ organisations non-profit	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.14.5.Commercial	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.14.6.Other	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
1.14a. If "other" in 1.14, specify	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
1.15. Coverage of the target population in terms of age	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.16. Coverage of the target population in terms of the sex of the respondents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
1.17. Comments relevant to variables in section 1	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
2. Information about the inclusion of the survey in the larger study			
2.1. ID number larger study (leave blank)	Open	No	-999.Not applicable (only if the survey is not part of a larger study; otherwise, this variable should have a response because it will be filled in by a central team)
2.2. Study Acronym	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.3. Name of the larger study Eng.	Open	No	-999.Not applicable (only if the survey is not part of a larger study; otherwise, this variable should have a response)
2.4. Name of the larger study Nat.	Open	No	-999.Not applicable (only if the survey is not part of a larger study; otherwise, this variable should have a response)
2.5. Name of other countries/regions/cities Eng.	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
In case of repeated/longitudinal surveys:			

2.6. Date of the first survey	Open	No	-99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.7. Frequency of waves/panels	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.8. Wave number	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
In the case of surveys that are a part of an international survey programme			
2.9. Date when the survey first became a part of international survey programme	Open	No	-99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.10. Frequency of waves since then	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
If sample is pooled:			
2.11. How many surveys pooled	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.12. Which other surveys pooled	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.12a. Pools emigrants from more than 1 country	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.13. Any qualitative studies linked to survey	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable **Please use -999.Not applicable if the survey does not belong to a larger study instead of "0.No". "0.No" should be used only when the survey belongs to a larger study and there is no qualitative component as part of the larger study.**

2.14. If "Yes", describe the studies	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
2.15. Additional comments to section 2	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
3.Ethnic and Migrant Target Population			
3.1. EMM target population: which minority group(s)	Open	No	N/A - must be filled out
3.1a. EMM target population with terms standardized	Open	No	N/A - must be filled out by the central team
3.2 Was the EMM target population	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
3.2a. If "other" in 3.2., describe which	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
3.3.Operalization of target population			
3.3.1.Country of birth of respondent	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.2.Country of birth of parents/grandparents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.3.Citizenship/nationality of respondent (current)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.4.Citizenship/nationality of respondent (at birth)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.5.Citizenship/nationality of parents/grandparents (current)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.6.Citizenship/nationality of parents/grandparents (at birth)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.7.Ethnic self-identification of respondent (one response allowed)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.8.Ethnic self-identification of respondent (multiple responses allowed)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.9.Ethnic self-identification of parents/grandparents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know

3.3.10.Mother tongue/language related question	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.11.Classification by interviewer	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.12.Classification by third agent /by proxy (e.g. by a government authority, and NGO, a social/cultural mediator, etc.)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.13.Classification by geographical location	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.14 Administrative/legal status	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.15.Through other means/characteristics	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3.16.Information not available on definition of target population	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.3a. If "other means" in 3.3., describe which	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
3.4. Migrant/minority related questions			
3.4.1.Country of birth of respondent	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.2.Country of birth of parents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.3.Country of birth of grandparents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.4.Nationality of respondent (current)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.5.Nationality of respondent (at birth)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.6.Nationality of parents (current)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.7.Nationality of grandparents (current)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.8.Nationality of parents (at birth)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know

3.4.9.Nationality of grandparents (at birth)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.10.Ethnic self-identification of respondent (one response allowed)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.11.Ethnic self-identification of respondent (multiple responses allowed)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.12.Ethnic self-identification of parents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.13.Ethnic self-identification of grandparents	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.14.Mother tongue/language related question	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.15.Classification by interviewer	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.4.16.Information not available on migrant/minority related questions	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
3.5. Size of the EMM target pop. as a whole	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
3.6. Survey include subgroup of majority pop.	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
3.6a. Survey designed as a general population survey	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
3.7. Additional comments to section 3	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
4. Sampling Method			
4.1. Sampling strategy - closed	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
4.2. Sampling strategy - open	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
4.3. Sample design - full information	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
4.4. Sampling frame(s)	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
4.5. Sampling units	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available

4.6. Comments on sampling methods	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
5. Sample Size for the overall survey			
5.1. Total gross/issued sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
5.2. Total net/achieved sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
5.3. Overall response rate	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
5.4. Overall response rate calculated	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
5.5. If "other" in 5.4., describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
5.6. Comment on any known issues	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
5.7. Are weights provided	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
5.8. If weights: Please describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
5.9. Additional comments to section 5	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6. Sample Sizes for any subgroups in which the survey is partitioned			
6a1. SG1 Name of sub-group	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6a2. SG1 Gross/issued sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6a3. SG1 Net/achieved sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6a4. SG1 Response rate	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6a5. SG1 Overall response rate calculated	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable

6a6. SG1 If "other" in 6a5., describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6a7. SG1 Comment on any known issues	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6b1. SG2 Name of sub-group	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6b2. SG2 Gross/issued sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6b3. SG2 Net/achieved sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6b4. SG2 Response rate	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6b5. SG2 Overall response rate calculated	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6b6. SG2 If "other" in 6b5., describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6b7. SG2 Comment on any known issues	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6c1. SG3 Name of sub-group	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6c2. SG3 Gross/issued sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6c3. SG3 Net/achieved sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6c4. SG3 Response rate	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6c5. SG3 Overall response rate calculated	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6c6. SG3 If "other" in 6c5., describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable

6c7. SG3 Comment on any known issues	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6d1. SG4 Name of sub-group	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6d2. SG4 Gross/issued sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6d3. SG4 Net/achieved sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6d4. SG4 Response rate	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6d5. SG4 Overall response rate calculated	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6d6. SG4 If "other" in 6d5., describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6d7. SG4 Comment on any known issues	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6e1. SG5 Name of sub-group	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
6e2. SG5 Gross/issued sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6e3. SG5 Net/achieved sample	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6e4. SG5 Response rate	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6e5. SG5 Overall response rate calculated	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6e6. SG5 If "other" in 6e5., describe	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
6e7. SG5 Comment on any known issues	Open	No	-999.Not applicable

6.8. Additional comments to section 6	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
7. Data collection information			
7.1. Name of person/institution/institute that undertook fieldwork	Open	No	-99.Information not available
7.2. Data collection mode			
7.2.1. Face to face (PAPI)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.2. Face to face (CAPI)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.3. Telephone	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.4. Web / email survey	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.5. Paper self-administered (collected)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.6. Paper self-administered (postal)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.7 Self-administered questionnaire: Mobile text messaging interviewing (CAMI)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.8 Self-administered questionnaire: Computer-assisted (CASI)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.9. Other	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
7.2.10. Information not available	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
For personal interviews:			
7.3. Who interviewed	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
7.4. Interviewers spoke migrant languages	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
7.5. If "yes", which	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
7.5a. Migrant languages in ISO code	Open	No	-999. Not applicable

7.6. Questionnaire in migrant language	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
7.7. If "yes", which	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
7.7a. Questionnaire in migrant language in ISO code	Open	No	-999. Not applicable
7.8. Average duration/length of interview	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
7.9. Number of questions	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
7.10. Additional comments to section 7	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
8. Availability			
8.1. Availability of the survey	Closed	No	4.Unavailable 5.Unknown availability
8.2. If available, where is the dataset stored	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.3. ID number of archive where dataset is stored	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.4. DOI for the dataset	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.5. Access to complete dataset	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
8.6. Access to portions of dataset	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -999.Not applicable (full dataset accessible)
8.7. Access to aggregate data results	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
8.8. Restrictions for data access, describe which	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.9. Dataset language(s) available	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
8.9a. Dataset languages in ISO code	Open	No	-999.Not applicable

8.10. Availability of survey doc. & q'aire	Closed	No	4.Unavailable 5.Unknown availability
8.11. If available, where is the survey doc. stored	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.12. ID number of archive where survey doc. is stored	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.13. DOI for the documentation	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.14. If the technical documentation is available, standard used for the documentation	Closed	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.15. Language(s) in which technical survey documentation is available	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
8.15a. Language(s) of technical survey documentation in ISO code	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
8.16. Availability of the survey questionnaire for individual research use	Closed	No	4.Unavailable 5.Unknown availability
8.17. If available, where is the survey q'aire stored	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.18. Identification number of the archive / repository where questionnaire is stored	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.19. DOI for the questionnaire	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
8.20. Language(s) in which survey questionnaire is available	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
8.20a. Language(s) of survey questionnaire in ISO code	Open	No	-999.Not applicable

8.21. Comments relevant to variables in section 8 (on data availability)	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
9. Data producers, owners, distributors and citations			
9.1. Institution/team responsible for data production	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
9.2. Institution/team that owns the data	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
9.3. Institution/team distributing the dataset	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
9.4. Contact details for queries/request	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
9.5. Citation for dataset	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
9.6. Citation for technical documentation	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available
9.7. Citation(s) for any other publications	Open	No	-9.Don't know -99.Information not available -999.Not applicable
9.8. Comments:	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
10. Additional Information			
10.1 Data quality (for internal use only)	Closed	No	-9.Don't know
10.2. Add.info. Data quality	Open	No	-999.Not applicable
10.3. Sources of information	Open	No	N/A - must be filled out
10.4. Any other comments about the survey	Open	No	-999.Not applicable

Appendix D: Standardization Rules for Proper Nouns

Proper nouns need to be standardized within each template and across all of the templates. The table below provides specific instructions on how to handle each type of proper noun:

Type of proper noun	Format
Survey name	Full name of the survey, exactly as it appears. [Note: Specific instructions about how to code the survey name were provided in the guidelines document] Correct example: European Union Minorities and Discrimination Survey Incorrect example: EU Minorities and Discrimination Survey
Person's name	First name followed by the surname. Correct example: Jane Smith Incorrect example: Smith, Jane
Institutional name	Full name followed by the acronym (do not make one up) in parentheses. Correct example: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) Incorrect example: UNHCR
Geographical location (e.g. country, city, region)	Full legal name; no abbreviations. Correct example: France Incorrect example: FR